

IMPROVING THE COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION

¹Abilova Zulfiya Zhalgasbayevna, ²Suyerova Nursuliv Khusanovna

¹Tashkent branch of Samarkand State university of veterinary medicine, animal husbandry and biotechnology, English language assistant teacher

²Tashkent branch of Samarkand State university of veterinary medicine, animal husbandry and biotechnology, Russian language assistant teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8226303>

Abstract. *The article raises the question of changing the methodological and practical developments of the educational process in order to meet the requirements of modern computer training. For the first time in the scientific world, the means helping the development of imaginative thinking are classified as a separate type of communication means and the term figurative means of communication (abbreviated as FMC) is applied to them.*

Keywords: *methodology, communication, computer, verballity, non-verballism.*

The modern requirements for English language learning are very different from the ones we have recently. As a result of society's transition from an industrial society to an information technology society, the accelerated pace of life has also shown the need to rethink many approaches to learning problems. The main one is that traditional education lags behind the opportunities offered by modern information infrastructure.

We proceed from the concept that any exchange of information is one of the components of the communication process, which becomes a full-fledged communication only after developing a common meaning based on this information.

Since the entire educational process itself is a product of complete communication, when viewed from this perspective, it becomes clear that digital education lacks a clear end result - the development of shared meaning.

To clarify the above, let's turn to the essence of the concept of communication and its practical implementation in the information field of the educational process. In the scientific world, there are several terminological symbols for the concept of communication.

In order to exclude an ambiguous interpretation of the research topic, we highlight and analyze the two most common of them. In scientific works, the concepts of verbal and non-verbal communication and, similarly, the concepts of written and oral communication are widely used.

What is the difference between them and which one should we focus on in this article? According to E. T. Kenenboyev, the concepts of verbal and non-verbal communication, mainly terminologically, incorrectly reflect the nature of the communicative process they describe, because it is impossible to convey intact information to the interlocutor using only words or only gestures.

A real manifestation of the interaction of verbal and non-verbal means of communication is possible only when using the concepts of written and oral communication.

Without studying the evidence of this statement, we take it as a basis in our work, because in this case each of these definitions includes verbal and non-verbal components of communication.

The digital education system, for all its technological advances, in any case uses one of the above two methods in the process of data transfer.

In this context, it makes sense to consider the compatibility between the technical possibilities of digital education and the traditional use of information transfer methods.

Despite the revolutionary changes brought about by information technology, many teachers still have traditional patterns of written communication.

Historically, writing could not constitute a full-fledged communication process due to the lack of non-verbal components necessary for it, which could form a similar process in interaction with verbal components, although this was its task from the moment of its appearance.

"The vector of this interaction is the non-verbal means of communication (NVV) and the verbal means of communication (VVV) moving towards the exact correspondence of written communication to oral communication."

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